
Study of Home Loan in ICICI Bank in Phaltan Area

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The objective of this paper is to understand the conceptual framework of home loan in India and to undertake the empirical study on home loan industry. In this regard secondary data is being used. The various issues related to drivers of demand in housing, evolution of home loan. Housing in India, importance and types of home loan have been discussed. Through this paper the basics of housing loan addressed.

Home is an integral part of a human being, who since his childhood, dreams to have living space of his own. Once in a lifetime investment requires loan to do it and that is how the home loan comes into scheme of things. Buying a home is dream for everyone. Due to the rising price of properties, it has almost become impossible for an average earning person to buy a home through lump sum payment. Therefore, the concept of home loan has come into existence. There are plethora of housing finance institutions and banks both in public and private sector which offer home loans.

Choosing one institution and one offer for home loan amidst the thousands available options have become a very complex task in our country. Apart from this, there are intricate business jargons and technicalities that make this job more tough and difficult. Through this study, I propose to identify the critical factors impacting the growth and distinguishing the growth pattern in home loan

portfolio particularly in public sector banks in India.

ICICI Bank is India's No. 1 Home Loans Provider. At ICICI Bank Home Loans, it offers unbeatable benefits to ensure that the customers get the best deal without any hassles and ICICI Bank makes it extremely easy for them.

Types of Home Loan:

Various types of home loans are available in India. They are described below:

- **Home Purchase Loan:**

These are the basic home loans for the purchase of a new house. These loans are given for purchase of a new or already built flat/bungalow/row-house.

- **Home Improvement Loan:**

These loans are given for implementing repair works and renovations in a home that has already been purchased by the customer. It may be requested for external works like structural repairs, waterproofing or internal works like tiling and flooring, plumbing, electrical work, painting, etc.

- **Home Construction Loan:**

These loans are available for the construction of a new home. The documents required by the banks for granting customer a home construction loan are slightly different from the home purchase loans. Depending upon the fact that when customer bought the land, the lending party would or would not include the

land cost as a component, to value the total cost of the property.

- **Home Extension Loan:**

Home Extension Loans are given for expanding or extending an existing home. For example, addition of an extra room etc. For this kind of loan, customer needs to have requisite approvals from the relevant municipal corporation.

- **Land Purchase Loan:**

Land Purchase Loans are available for purchase of land for both home construction or investment purposes. Therefore, customer can be granted this loan even if customer is not planning to construct any building on it soon. However, customer must complete construction within tenure of three years on the same land.

- **Bridge Loan:**

Bridge Loans are designed for people who wish to sell the existing home and purchase another. The bridge loan helps finance the new home, until a buyer is found for the old home.

- **Balance Transfer:**

Balance Transfer loans help customer to pay off an existing home loan and avail the option of a loan with a lower rate of interest. Customer can transfer the balance of the existing home loan to any another bank.

- **NRI Home Loan:**

This is a special home loan scheme for the Non-Resident Indians (NRI) who wishes to build or buy a home or land property in India. They are offered attractive housing finance plans with suitable reimbursement options by many banks in the country.

The housing is one of the basic needs of the people as it ranks next to food and clothing. A certain minimum standard of housing is essential for a healthy and civilized living. Thus, the priority has to be given for the development of housing in a country. It is a tool for modern economic development. The census records of India exhibits that there was no deficit-housing

problem in India till the first half of the century. In 1901, there were 55.8 million houses for 54 million households showing a surplus of 1.8 million houses. This surplus situation continued till 1941. It was only after 1951, the deficit trend has started and is continuing with an escalating magnitude. In 1971, total number of households was 100.4 million and the number of houses was 90.7 million, showing a deficit of 9.7 million. The housing shortage during 2001 was 41 million. The estimated housing stock requirement in the country by 2021 is about 77 million in urban areas and 63 million in rural areas. The increasing number of houses and a rising trend in the size of the households has contributed to the shortage of housing stock in the urban areas. Only 20% of the Indian population lived in urban areas in 1970 (UNDP 1998). The urbanization is expected to increase still. This resulted in an estimation of 36% of the population to live in urban areas by 2015. In India, there is a very widening gap between the supply and demand for housing. There is an urgent need to modify the policy on one hand and look for an innovative approach for construction of houses on the other to reduce the deficit. The Government of India (GoI) had introduced schemes and projects for housing problem in every five-year plans. The National Housing Policy formulated by government of India considers the developments on national and international scene on shelter sector. The adoption of National Housing Policy by the Parliament in 1994 was a landmark step in promoting housing development in the country.

Research Methodology:

This paper is based on primary data of 100 respondents and random sampling method is used. Questionnaire is prepared and data collected and analysed and interpreted using charts and tables.

Hypothesis:

- **Null Hypothesis (H₀):** There is no significant relationship between time taken to process the loan and disbursement of loan.
- **Alternate Hypothesis (H₁):** There is a significant relationship between time taken to process the loan and disbursement of loan.

Research Design:

Type of Design	Exploratory Research Design.
Sample size	The sample comprises of 100 respondents
Research Area	Phaltan Branch
Sampling Technique	Random Sampling

- * Questionnaire Preparation
- * Collecting Data from Employee
- * Analysis of Data
- * Testing of Hypothesis
- * Analyzing using SPSS Tools

Questionnaire Preparation:

The questionnaire is prepared based on the need of present employees working due to recent changes working style and to get updated with current technology.

Analysis of Data:

The Collected Data obtained is analyzed and interpreted using charts and tables.

Testing of Hypothesis:

Hypothesis is tested using SPSS Package.

Analysing using SPSS Tools:

The data is imported in SPSS and analyzed using required tools.

Need For Study:

- The business environment today and intense competition globally have made it mandatory.
- The business entities to train their human resources constantly and as per the emerging challenges.

- The Major three needs are to understand the home loan market with its current practices in context of Indian scenario.
- To know the ideas of customers about home loan products and services.
- To study the problem faced by the customers in obtaining home loan.
- Designed strategically to meet the business needs.

Objective of the Study:

- Following are the objectives of the study:
- To understand the concept of home loans schemes.
- To understand the documents involved in the home loans and the repayment methodology.
- To detail about the interest rates and tenure to be chosen for repayment.
- To know more about the innovative home loan schemes and the risk capturing mechanisms.

Scope of the Study:

All industries have challenges to face when it comes to training their workforce, many of which are unique to that particular industry, and the banking sector is no different.

- Regulation changes
- Ensuring all staff meet training standards
- Resistance to change
- Supplementing existing courses
- Overwhelming levels of information

Limitations of Study:

- The study is confined to Satara District only due to time audit
- Getting timely responses from the respondents was a difficult task due to their regular routine activities.
- The data collected for the research is fully on primary data given by the respondents. There is chance for personal bias, so the accuracy is not true.
- The study has been limited 100 respondents only.

- Limited time for survey is other constrain.

Data Analysis and Interpretation of Data:

Percentage Analysis:

Table 1: Gender

Gender	No of Respondents	Percentage
Male	60	60%
Female	40	40%

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is found that 60% of respondents are Males and remaining 40% are females.

Chart 1: Gender

Table 2: Occupation

Occupation	No. Of Respondent	Percentage
Govt. Employee	18	18%
Private Employee	37	37%
Self- Employed Professional	23	23%
Self Employed Non-Professional	14	14%
Unemployed	8	8%

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is found that majority of 37% of respondents are from private employee.

Chart 2: Occupation

Table 3: Income

Income	No. Of Respondent	Percentage
Below 2Lakhs	15	15%
2-6 Lakhs	23	23%
6-12 Lakhs	37	37%
Above 12Lakhs	25	25%

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is found that 15% of respondents receive income below 2lakhs ,23% of respondents receive 2-6 lakhs, 37% of respondents receive income 6- 12lakhs and 25% of respondents receive above 12lakhs.

Chart 3: Income

Table 4: Category of House

Category of House	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Own House	70	70%
Rental House	30	30%

The data in Table 5 indicates that 70% of the respondents reside in their own houses, while the remaining 30% live in rental houses.

Table 5: Ownership

Ownership	No. Of Respondent	Percentage
Parents	36	36%
Spouse	32	32%
Relative	8	8%
Others	24	24%

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is found that 36% of respondents owner is their parents, 32% of respondents owner is their spouse, 8% of respondents owner is their relatives and 24% of respondents owner is others.

Chart 6: Ownership

Table 7: Primary Bank

Primary Bank	No. Of Respondent	Percentage
ICICI Bank	65	65%
HDFC Bank	10	10%
Axis Bank	7	7%
Govt. Sector Banks	18	18%

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is found that 65% of respondents primary bank is ICICI

Bank, 10% of respondents in HDFC Bank, 7% of respondents in Axis Bank and 18% of respondents in Govt. Sector Banks.

Chart 7: Primary Bank

Table 8: Preferred Bank for Home Loan

Primary Bank	No. Of Respondent	Percentage
Primary Bank	65	65%
Other Bank	35	35%

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is found that 65% of respondents prefer primary bank for home loan and remaining 35% prefer home loan for other banks.

Chart 9: Status of preferred bank for Home Loan

Table 9: Status of Home Loan

Status of Home Loan	No. Of Respondent	Percentage
New Home Loan	90	90%
Existing Home Loan	10	10%

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is found that 90% of respondents are new home loan customers and remaining 10% are existing home loan customers.

Chart 9: Status of Home Loan

Type of Loan	No. Of Respondent	%
Construction Loan	35	35%
Buying Flat/House	26	26%
Balance Transfer	9	9%
Land Loan	11	11%
PMAY	19	19%

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is found that 35% of respondents take construction loan, 26% of respondents take loan for buying flat/house, 9% respondents transfer their balance, 11% respondents take land loan & remaining 19% respondents take PMAY loan.

Table 11: Repayment Tenure

Repayment Tenure	No. Of Respondent	Percentage
5-10years	30	30%
10-20 years	65	65%
30 Years	5	5%

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is found that majority of 65% prefer repayment between 10-20years.

Chart 11: Repayment Tenure

Table 12: Extension Loan

Extension Loan	No. Of Respondent	Percentage
Repulsion and Renovation	35	35%
Additional Extended Loan	65	65%

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is found that majority of 65% prefer additional extended loan.

Chart 12: Extension Loan

Findings, Suggestions and Conclusions:

Findings:

- Majority (60%) of the respondents are Male.
- Majority (37%) of the respondents are occupied as private employee.
- Majority (37%) of the respondent’s income is between 6-12Lakhs p.a.
- Majority (81%) of the respondents prefer individual type of villa.
- Majority (70%) of the respondents are presently living in their own house.
- Majority (36%) of the respondents’ resident owners are their parents.
- Majority (65%) of the respondents have their primary account in ICICI BANK.

- Majority (65%) of the respondents prefer their primary bank to take further loan.
- Majority (90%) of the respondents says that prefer to take fresh new loan.
- Majority (35%) of the respondents are interested in taking loan as construction for home.
- Majority (65%) of the respondent prefer their repayment between 10-20years.
- Majority (65%) of the respondents also prefer to take additional extended loan for further extension.

Conclusion:

- In my study we came to know that many peoples are interested to take a home loan from ICICI bank to construct their homes.
- Home loans have long period when compare to other personal loans and other loans. So peoples are interested to take a home loan as it becomes an asset.
- Even though the interest rates are high peoples are willing to take a loan from ICICI bank due to quick process and sanctioning with expert teams.
- The loan sanction process is much faster when compare to other banks.
- For disbursement process is also it will take less time and less number of stages when compare to other banks.
- Finally, Home Loan is best income for banks for long time and customers also get their dreams fulfilled.

Suggestions:

- ICICI Bank having good brand image in the minds of customers.
- Majority of the people got loans from ICICI Bank only.
- Most of the customers are not aware of the products of ICICI home loans.
- Some of the customer's felt that the interest rates are somewhat high.
- Some of the customer not having good faith on private banks.
- Most of the people are directly go to bank to apply a home loan.
- Some of the customer of ICICI already benefited through ICICI home loan products and services.

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